

Large whale entanglements, strandings, ice entrapments and selective marine animal sightings reported to the Whale Release and Strandings Group in Newfoundland and Labrador and a summary of the Whale Release and Strandings Program during 2024

A Report to the Department of Fisheries and Oceans, Canada –
Newfoundland and Labrador Region

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The Canadian Coast Guard Marine Traffic Centers diligently report entrapped and stranded marine animals and sightings regularly to the hotline. Thanks for the service.

To the harvesters of the Newfoundland Region who have continued to support Whale Release and Strandings program throughout its long history, the success of our work releasing entrapped marine animals would not be possible without your continued support and participation.

Whale Release and Strandings Group

The Whale Release and Strandings Group (Tangly Whales, Inc.) is a non-profit environmental organization responsible for the disentanglement and response to strandings of marine animals in Newfoundland and Labrador since 2000 and incorporated in July 2002. The organization has a board of directors.

The Mission statement for the Whale Release and Strandings Group is:

- To conserve biodiversity
- To release whales from fishing gear
- To attempt to save fishing gear to the extent possible during a disentanglement
- To coordinate strandings on marine animals
- To conduct research work on marine animals
- To conduct all other work on marine animals as seen fit.

From 1978 through 2024 assistance has been offered to harvesters in the Newfoundland Region who incidentally have large whales, leatherback sea turtles and basking sharks entangled in their fishing gear and for live stranded marine animals. This service has been provided with support and cooperation from Fisheries and Oceans, Canada.

Summary reports

During this time-period (1978-2024) information from harvesters regarding whale interactions has been recorded and monitored. Included are the incidences of entrapments, strandings and sightings of leatherback sea turtles, sharks and 20 different species of cetaceans have that been recorded in continuous reports and summaries from 1978 - 2023.

This report represents the forty-eight (48th) of such reports in a similar format produced by the Whale Research Group and the Whale Release and Strandings Group. The purpose of these reports is to summarize yearly activities of important events such as entrapments/entanglements/strandings/sightings of animals at risk and under study, research and/or educational studies undertaken. These entanglement reports are catalogued at the Memorial University of Newfoundland and Labrador Library (Centre for Newfoundland Studies), Fisheries and Oceans Canada, on Zenodo.org. and with the Whale Release and Strandings Group. One of the benefits of these reports is quick access to changes in entrapments and entanglements in the Newfoundland Region related to changes in fishing gear and distributions of large marine animals as well as the various strandings, ice-entrapments and strandings and sightings of rare animals and animals under study.

Introduction

The program, which has been run by the Whale Release and Strandings Group (WRS) from 2001-2024, plus providing during 2000 a one-year mentorship with the Canadian Coast Guard, uses methods of which the most important is working with stakeholders (harvesters) for disentangling of large whales from fishing gear, which was pioneered by Dr. Jon Lien (Lien 1980) and with a few modifications, these methods remain those of choice today.

The disentanglement program in use today was designed and developed for the highly rural nature of over 800 fishing communities spread over the 17,000 km coastline of Newfoundland and Labrador (NL). The disentanglement assistance program has benefited harvesters, whales, leatherback sea turtles and the people of Canada. It provides assistance to often financially stretched harvesters, saving them thousands of dollars in what would be lost fishing gear and downtime if they did not have skilled support in releasing a large whale entrapped in their gear. It releases large and often endangered whales, leatherback sea turtles and basking shark from fishing gear and allows them to continue their life processes. We have the largest feeding population of humpbacks in the northwest Atlantic, with about 5,000 individuals visiting NL waters during spring, summer, and fall. These whales are the basis for a large tourism industry in the region.

The program also responds to all reported live and dead cetaceans and sea turtles, floating and stranded, as well as pack ice entrapments.

The purpose of the assistance is: (1) to assist fishers in releasing whales from fishing gear, thus decreasing downtime and damage to fishing gear. The length of time a large marine animal is entrapped in fishing gear is directly correlated to greater gear damage and loss of income due to the gear not fishing properly or at all (Lien 1983), (2) to release entrapped marine animals as quickly and safely as possible to allow them to continue their life processes, such as feeding, migrating, mating, rearing their young, (3) to communicate with harvesters and communities about marine animals, including species at risk, habitat protection, and (4) to add to the scientific knowledge of cetaceans, leatherback sea turtles and sharks that inhabit Newfoundland and Labrador waters.

Fish harvesters have come to realize that calling a government sponsored program offers them a faster and more efficient alternative to dealing with a gear-entrapped animal than attempting a release on their own. Harvesters and untrained persons who take whales out of gear often leave large amounts of fishing gear on the animal perhaps because they do not or cannot look underwater to see all the gear that is on the entrapped animal. Whales caught in crab gear that are cut loose by harvesters and other untrained persons are often released with vast amounts of rope and pots still attached (Ledwell and Huntington 2001, 2002, 2006). This provides more opportunity for whale re-entrapment and more gear damage and allows the animal to move from the vicinity in which it was entrapped and be difficult to relocate, and/or difficult to catch to remove the gear still on it. A timely response by experienced personnel results in the removal of most if not all gear from the animals, less gear damage and fishing downtime, particularly important to the economically marginalized inshore harvesters.

From 1979 to 2024 two thousand and thirty-three (2033) humpback whales (*Megaptera novaeangliae*), one hundred and sixty-four (164) minke whales (*Balaenoptera acutorostrata*), fourteen (14) fin whales (*Balaenoptera physalus*), two right whales (*Eubalaena glacialis*), one bowhead whale (*Balaena mysticetus*) and eighty-eight (88) unknown large whales were reported entrapped or entangled in fishing gear in Newfoundland and Labrador.

Eighty-two (82) leatherback turtles (*Dermochelys coriacea*) have been reported entangled in fishing gear in this region with a mortality of 25%. There have been seventeen (17) reported leatherback turtle strandings with 13 of those being dead animals reported in the region. Two (2) live leatherbacks that had stranded were rescued and returned to sea by members of the WRS group. A loggerhead turtle (*Caretta caretta*) was collected cold stunned in Hermitage harbour and returned to ocean from the Harbour Breton harbour after it was rewarmed (Ledwell and Huntington 2007).

Entrapments, strandings and sightings of other cetaceans either unusual to the area or under study or animals free swimming but in poor health and marine animals such as sea turtles, sharks, walrus have also been documented

From 1992 to 2000 funding for a marine animal release program was varied and at times non-existent.

The most common types of fishing gear associated with entanglements in this region currently includes gillnets (cod, herring, mackerel, lumpfish, flounder, monk, skate and turbot) snow crab pots, whelk pots, toad crab pots, box traps (caplin, cod, herring, mackerel and squid), unspecified and illegal gillnets, ropes/buoys and moorings. In other words, most types of fishing gear have the potential to incidentally catch whales and they do. In recent years fishing effort in Newfoundland and Labrador has shifted offshore. This shift in gear has led to an increase in the number of offshore entrapments reported and offshore entanglements have primarily involved snow crab and whelk pot gear.

Methods

Whale, leatherback turtle and basking shark entanglements in fishing gear and strandings and sightings of marine animals were reported to the Whale Release and Strandings Program in 2024 by calling an advertised toll-free number (1-888-895-3003) which can be accessed 24 hours a day seven-days a week year around. A trained release team responds by providing suitable, safe advice or sending expert personnel to the site for needed assistance. The trained crew is equipped and ready to deploy immediately with an inflatable zodiac and necessary specialized tools for disentanglement of whales, leatherback sea turtles and basking sharks. The objective of each disentanglement is the safe, clean (complete) release of the whale or other marine animals from the fishing gear and minimal or no damage to the fishing gear involved in the entanglement. The disentanglement crew also responded to whale and leatherback turtle strandings. Calls concerning entanglements, strandings and dead floating animals were also forwarded to the group by harvesters, DFO Conservation Officers, Coast Guard Centers, Royal

Canadian Mounted Police (RCMP), Crime Stoppers and the public. Fisheries and Oceans Canada funded the program in 2024.

Results and Discussion

Results of the Entrapment Assistance Program from previous years have been summarized in annual reports to Fisheries and Oceans and the Newfoundland and Labrador Department of Fisheries (Lien 1980; Lien and Aldrich 1982; Lien et al. 1982; 1983; 1984; 1985; 1986; 1987; 1988; 1989; Lien 1990; 1991; 1992; 1993; 1994; 1995; 1996; Ledwell, Huntington and Lien 2000; Ledwell and Huntington 2001; 2002; 2003; 2004; 2005; 2006; 2007; 2008; 2009; Ledwell, Huntington and Kelly 2010; Ledwell and Huntington 2011; 2012; Ledwell, Huntington and Sacrey 2013; 2014; 2015; Ledwell and Huntington 2016; Ledwell, Huntington and Enserink 2017; Ledwell, Huntington and Ledwell 2018; Ledwell, Huntington and Sacrey 2019; Ledwell, Huntington, Ledwell, and Landry 2020; Ledwell, Huntington, Landry and Ledwell 2021, Ledwell, Huntington, Sacrey and Landry 2022; Ledwell, Huntington and Landry 2023).

Humpback Whales (Table 1)

26th-28th February. Terrenceville, Fortune Bay

Humpback, reported by turr hunters, heavily entangled on the 26th February near Terrenceville, Fortune Bay. WRS requested conservation officers from Marystown to check the area on the morning of the 27th. They relocated the whale in the same area but the wind was too heavy for a response. The whale was relocated close to noon on the 28th and WRS conducted a response with DFO officers standing by. The whale, anchored in heavy gear, had a bridle wrap with two 9/16” ropes over its back, a small white poly buoy jammed tight into the right side of mouth. We cut the bridle rope that was through its mouth and around its head and one of the ropes but the second rope was embedded into the back and we couldn't get our cutting knife under it. We lashed a handheld knife onto a pole, cut into the whale and the rope. We then worked on the float. We managed to hold it and cut at the neck of the float as the neck was also tight to its mouth. We then used our cutting grapple to cut the weight from under the whale which was also around its pectoral. We did this in diminishing light and the weight let go. We didn't see anything else on the animal except the float was still against its mouth although we had cut a fair bit of the neck of the float. It blew a storm for the next 3 days but the turr hunters and DFO conservation officers said the whale was gone. We do not know the type of gear.

27th April. New Harbour, Trinity Bay

Humpback caught in herring net mooring ropes. The whale was caught through the mouth with another rope going over its back. With the help of the fishermen who reported it we had to ascertain which ropes were which as we didn't want to cut the rope that was holding it since the whale could then swing into the net and become further entangled. The whale had a lot of mobility, staying under for lengthy periods and surfacing out of reach. We cut the rope going over its back and the holding rope that was through its mouth and around its head. Whale was released gear free.

4th May. Summerville, Bonavista Bay

Humpback entangled in herring net moorings. This whale was in constant motion and very difficult to work on. There had been over a week of strong northeasters throughout

the region and on the 4th May when the whale was discovered it was at times ashore on rocks and entangled. There was a breaking rock very close to the animal. The whale was entangled in very shoal water moving close to the rock and close to touching shore while we worked at it. It was caught through the mouth which was also tied to its pectoral fin and a large grapnel holding the gear and whale in the area. There was no net on the herring frame. We removed the bridal rope by cutting the rope close to its mouth. The animal was very active, slashing its tail at us. We managed to cut the rope from around its pectoral fin, but the animal did not want to leave where it was even though there was no more gear holding it in place. We tried to shepherd it out of the area as there was another herring net in the area, but it kept returning to where it was entangled close to shore. We believe that the whale was entangled for multiple days without being discovered during high winds and rough water and it's possible it had been stranded against the shore rocks. When the weather cleared hikers discovered it. Because of its time ashore and not swimming we believe the animal was disorientated. We left the whale with only a short piece of rope remaining on its pectoral. The animal left the area later that evening. The gear was local and we gave it to the DFO Conservation Officers to give back to the harvester.

10th May. Swale Island (Happy Adventure), Bonavista Bay

Humpback heavily entangled in herring net with rope, netting and lead rope wrapped over its head, through mouth and around left pectoral. There were 6 poly buoys wrapped around the gear and whale with dozens of fresh herring still in the net rolling around the animal. We removed the head wraps after over an hour trying to get close to the whale as it was constantly turning in very shoal water close to a shoal which was breaking also. We then went to work on the left side of the animal removing the anchoring ropes and all the netting, floats, rope, lead ropes from the pectoral fin. WRS gave the net and floats to DFO Conservation Officers. The gear was local.

12th June. Jackman Canyon, Grand Banks

Humpback cut out of snow crab gear by harvesters aboard the FV Grand Retriever on the Grand Banks 230nm from St. Johns. The whale was left towing 45 m of 9/16" polysteel rope and 2 large poly buoys. The whale was caught in the haul up rope and became wild while they were trying to take the gear off of it. They were scared for their safety and cut it away with gear listed above. WRS was patched through via Coast Guard traffic and consulted with the skipper on the fishing vessel. Entangled humpbacks are extremely dangerous with vessels carrying stabilizers as the animal can get caught on the stabilizer fin (the fish) and possibly capsize the boat (Ledwell and Huntington 2004).

18th June. St. Anthony Cape

Humpback entrapped in fleet of two lumpfish nets. WRS team left afternoon of the 18th. Arrived in St. Anthony (14-hour drive) early morning of the 19th. The whale was reported still entangled daylight on the 19th but broke free an hour before the team arrived. WRS with DFO Conservation Officers from St. Anthony searched the area all morning to no luck. Never saw a whale.

30th June. 2 nm off Fermuese, Southern Shore

Humpback, reported to WRS at 0750 by DFO surveillance plane, as thrashing violently with a red poly buoy attached in the pectoral area. The plane passed the message to the FV Clears Cove Pride who also contacted us. The fishing vessel did not see the whale but

said they would send one of their crew out in a speed boat for support for us as they had a load of crab to unload in Fermuese. We asked the plane to do another flyover and they did but fog had set in. WRS was ready to go but the wind picked up too much to mount a response. Animal not relocated.

2nd-11th August. Bear Cove Point, Fermuese

A concerned citizen took drone footage of what he thought was a humpback in distress. He couldn't see any gear on it and didn't resight the whale early next morning. On the 11th a harvester who has been on various disentanglements with us said there was a whale in the same area for 3 days in the area of the 2nd August report. WRS responded and located the whale which was not moving. The animal had poor body condition and looked thin. We checked the whale out. It wasn't entangled but remained in the same area all the while we were there observing it.

29th September. Mainland, South West coast

A local hiker reported seeing a whale very close to shore continually "bawling" with a small red float attached to it. WRS asked Stephenville DFO Conservation Officers to check it out. They reported only seeing a gear free minke whale breaching in the area.

Strandings (Table 3)

26th July. Mass stranding White sided dolphins. St. Georges

Six (6) white sided dolphins live stranded in Red Rocks, St. Georges Bay. WRS corresponded with locals on getting the animals back to deep water. The dolphins were pushed back out and not seen after.

23rd August. Pygmy Sperm whale. Portugal Cove South

A pygmy sperm whale live stranded on the beach at Portugal Cove South on the Southern Shore. WRS advised the locals on trying to move the animal back to deep water. The animal re-stranded and we advised them to leave it as it wanted to die. The animal died shortly afterwards and WRS members conducted a field necropsy in Portugal Cove South. All tissue, organs were sampled and teeth removed for sectioning. Samples, images were provided to DFO Marine Mammals section, St. Johns.

3rd September. Northern Bottlenose whale. Sops Arm, White Bay

A decomposing Northern Bottlenose whale was discovered by a cabin owner on the beach. WRS was alerted and alerted DFO Springdale who took measurements and samples for DFO Marine Mammals in St. John's. Interestingly a Northern Bottlenose whale was photographed swimming in the area 3 weeks prior to this stranding. We believe this could be the same animal. Many times, these types of whales that strand and die have been seen in the area from a few days to a week or more before deciding to strand and die.

1st, 23rd July, 20th September pilot whales and 7th July humpback (Table 3). Partially eaten carcasses

Three (3) pilot whales and one (1) humpback were discovered dead with large sections of

their bodies missing. The teeth marks in the blubber and tissue seem to be from predation from large sharks.

Sightings (Table 4)

8th July. Beluga. Chance Cove, Trinity Bay

An adult beluga was observed feeding on caplin in Chance Cove, Trinity Bay.

11th August. Northern Right whale. Fogo Island

A right whale was photographed feeding in Back Cove, Fogo Island. WRS was alerted to a different whale seen in the area. We contacted the DFO Fogo Island and had them photo the animal. Images sent to J. Lawson of Marine Mammals, St. John's and on to the New England Aquarium for possible identification.

1st September. Three (3) Blue whales. Trinity

From the 1st to the 3rd of September the tour group Sea of Whales photographed 3 blue whales off New Bonaventure head in Trinity Bay.

Education Activities

We were contracted to CPAWS Newfoundland and Labrador to present for their “Open Standards for Community Engagement” program. WRS travelled to Bay d’Espoir Academy, St. Albans and Se’t A’Newey Kina’m’kuom (St. Anne’s School), Conne River for interactive presentations on the whales of Newfoundland and Labrador. In February 2024 we engaged South Coast Communities on Aquatic Species at Risk during community and school presentations over several days, as well as a session on cetacean identification to the Miawpukek First Nation (MFN) Guardians.

Travel to Labrador North Coast

Between the months of April and May, Tangly Whales' outreach program provided engaging and interactive marine wildlife education sessions with selected pieces that complemented grade-specific curriculum and focused on local species and their conservation.

During this time, Tangly Whales was able to reach two schools within the Nunatsiavut, Labrador Region, with sessions taking place at Jens Haven Memorial School in both elementary and secondary schools (for classes including kindergarten up to grade 12) in Nain, and at Amos Comenius Memorial School in Hopedale. We were also able to visit the Children, Seniors and Social Development Child centre to engage with preschool children in Hopedale.

Although plans were also in place to reach two additional communities, Rigolet and Natuashish, during this time, adverse weather conditions grounded flights between communities for several days and, unfortunately, we were unable to reach them at this time. However, both communities request our visit be postponed to a later date and we are hopeful this will be possible.

Recommendations

Recommendation 1. Funding agreements should be in place and funds available before

entrapment season begins. Agreements need to be established that are assurances to provide support to an organized program over a period of years. Programs that do not have these assurances will be very difficult to maintain and staff on an on-going basis (Lien 2004).

Recommendation 2. All licensed fishing vessels in the Newfoundland region should have the toll-free number stickers onboard alerting them who to call when they have an entrapped or stranded whale or see an entrapped or stranded whale or leatherback sea turtle. By having the toll-free number visible in the wheelhouse, harvesters may decide to call for expert advice when they have or see a whale or leatherback entrapped and not attempt to cut animals free and leave them with large amounts of gear attached which may cause the animal to die or become re-entrapped. This situation can be at least partially avoided if boats have the entrapment assistance hot line number easily visible onboard and upon calling can be advised on the proper release procedures or be advised that a release team is available to attend to the entanglement. This may lessen the number of whales or sea turtles each season swimming around with large amounts of snow crab and other gear attached. See Appendix I for toll-free sticker.

Because of the dangers inherent in fishing boats encountering entangled large whales in their fishing gear in the offshore, especially snow crab gear, fishing groups need to be advised by an experienced disentanglement group on procedures to protect lives and lessen gear entanglement.

Table 1. Humpback whales reported entangled in fishing gear in Newfoundland and Labrador during 2024

Date	Area	Gear type	Description
26 th -28 th February	Terrenceville, Fortune Bay. 4739N, 5447W	Heavy rope, small poly buoy	Whale must have been anchored in something heavy. Released gear free by WRS team
27 th April	New Harbour, Trinity Bay. 4736N, 5337W	Herring net moorings	Released gear free by WRS team
4 th May	Summerville, Bonavista Bay. 4827N, 5333W	Herring net frame	Very difficult whale. Released gear free by WRS team
10 th May	Off Happy Adventure, Bonavista Bay. 4836N, 5343W	Herring net	Released gear free by WRS team
12 th June	Jackman Canyon, Grand Banks. 4317N, 4937W	Snow crab fleet	Wild whale cut free by fishing crew and towing buoys 45m of 9/16” polysteel rope and 2 large poly buoys
15 th June	St. John’s. 4757N, 5267W	White rope	Whale reported by Ocean Quest boat tours swimming north with short length of white rope over back. Unable to relocate
18 th June	St. Anthony Cape. 5135N, 5552W	2 lumpfish nets	Whale broke free 1 hour before WRS team arrived. Searched area all morning with no success to relocate
30 th June	2nm off Fermuese, Southern Shore. 4658N, 5251W	Rope and red poly buoy	DFO surveillance plane reported the whale but we were unable to relocate it nor was the plane and the FV Clears Cove Pride
3 rd July	Ship Cove, Placentia Bay. 4710N, 5409W	Whale with rope and small “lobster” float attached	Unable to relocate animal
4 th July	St Anthony Bight.	Rope and small white float	Reported by tour boat operator. Whale not resighted
18 th July	Biscayne Cove, Pouch Cove. 4780N, 5279W	Rope and float	Whale towing ~ 10m rope and small fishing float
21 st July	Bonavista lighthouse. 4880N, 5314W	Rope	Rope wrapped around pectoral fin. Not towing anything. Reported by tour boat Discovery Adventure

			Tours. Not resighted
22 nd July	Ferryland lighthouse, Southern Shore. 4701N, 5286W	Fishing float dragging behind flukes	WRS responded but the wind freshened and were unable to relocate whale after 2 days searching by water and land
2 nd -11 th August	Bear Cove lighthouse, Southern Shore. 4656N, 5253W	Suspected entangled	Whale in same area for multiple days. Checked by WRS team on the 11 th . Animal in same area with no gear on it
29 th September	Mainland, South West coast. 4833N, 5914W	Suspected entangled	Local said the whale was close to shore “bawling” with small red float on it

Table 2. Leatherback sea turtle strandings/sightings reported in Newfoundland and Labrador during 2024

Date	Area	Description
13 th August	Fortune Bay.	4 leatherbacks reported by Aquaculture vessel free swimming
13 th August	SE Sagona Island, Fortune Bay. 4721N, 5546W	Leatherback free swimming reported by DFO Harbour Breton

Table 3. Stranded and dead floating cetaceans reported in Newfoundland reported during 2024

Date	Area	Species	Description
15 th January	Catalina, Bonavista Bay. 4851N, 5307W	Pilot whale	Locals concerned of pilot whale in area for several days. Animal eventually moved on
6 th February	Wild Cove, Notre Dame Bay. 4940N, 5446W	White beaked dolphin	Dead stranded
23 rd May	4708N, 4908W	Small cetacean	Possible dead floating minke
9 th June	2nm south Cape Pine, St. Mary's Bay. 4634N, 5332W	Large whale spp; dead drifting	Contacted DFO for further possible sighting
9 th June	Griquet, Great Northern Peninsula. 5152N, 5545W	Pilot whale	Dead stranded (?)
11 th June	Griquet, Great Northern Peninsula. 5152N, 5545W	Pilot whale	Free swimming in the harbour close to shore for several days. DFO checked it out. Animal stayed there for a week and disappeared
17 th June	Cape Freels, Bonavista Bay. 4923N, 5348W	Minke whale	Dead stranded on portion of Cape Island facing Cobbler Island
20 th June	Kippens, West Coast. 4832N, 5836W	Harbour porpoise	Dead on beach with rope cut into body forward of dorsal fin. Dorsal fin almost severed
21 ST June	Elliston, Bonavista Bay. 4862N, 5302W	Minke	Dead floating and stranded. Animal in severe stage of decomposition
1 st July	Point La Haye beach, St. Mary's Bay. 4690N, 5361W	Pilot whale	Dead on beach. Large posterior section of animal missing with bite marks of large shark evident on remaining body
7 th July	5NM north of Baccelieu Island, Conception Bay. 4814N, 5245W	Humpback	Dead drifting with large stomach section bitten by what looks like large shark teeth. Reported by CCGS Ann Harvey.
20 th July	South St. Pierre. 4637N, 5623W	Humpback	Dead drifting message sent by vessel Equinox through Placentia MCTS
23 rd July	Pass Island Hermitage Bay. 4729N, 5612W	Pilot whale	Long dead animal on beach with large section missing with large teeth marks from a shark

			evident
23rd July	Codroy Valley Provincial Park. 4783N, 5933W	Blue fin tuna	Large tuna live stranded and died
25 th July	Red Rocks, St. Georges	6 White sided dolphins	Live stranded and pushed back out by locals and volunteer fire department. WRS consulted with rescuers and DFO to coordinate the refloating
25 th July	Chamber Island, Placentia Bay	Sick dolphin	Reported close to shore swimming on right side. W. Ledwell said it was an animal that was going to strand. Not reported again
30 th July	Norris Arm, Notre Dame Bay.	Minke whale	Live stranded and died. Samples taken for DFO Marine Mammals St. John's
8 th August	Browns Harbour, Garnish, Fortune Bay. 4716N, 5518W	Sperm whale	15m male sperm whale dead stranded. Samples taken for DFO Marine Mammals St. John's
23 rd August	Portugal Cove South. 4642N, 4315W	Pygmy sperm whale	Pygmy sperm whale, <i>Kogia breviceps</i> , live stranded, was pushed back out but restranded and died. Necropsy conducted by WRS team
3 rd September	Sops Arm, White Bay. 4947N, 5651W	Northern bottlenose whale	Discovered by cabin owner. Animal "pretty cooked". DFO Springdale took samples for DFO marine mammals St. John's
4 th September	Shallow Bay, Great Northern Peninsula. 4956N, 5745W	Minke whale	Live stranded and died
6 th September	Holyrood Pond, St. Mary's Bay. 4647N, 5337W	Short fin mako shark	Dead on beach inside causeway in the pond
6 th September	Renews, Southern Shore. 4655N, 5256W	Harbour porpoise	Dead on beach
7 th September	Freshwater Bay, St. Johns. 4732N, 5241W	White sided dolphin	Discovered by hiker dead on beach
20 th September	Mainland, Lourdes South West coast. 4834N, 5910W	Minke whale	Dead on beach. Locals want removed due to stinking place up. W. Ledwell gave them contact for Provincial Govt. Works and Services

20 th September	Portugal Cove South. 4642N, 5315W	Pilot whale	Dead on beach with large body section missing. Shark-like teeth marks evident
9 th -16 th October	Fox Harbour, Placentia Bay. 4719N, 5354W	Pilot whale	Whale swimming close to shore, almost stranding in tidal zone various times. Animal not seen after the 16 th . WRS responded
15 th October	Port Union, Bonavista Bay. 4830N, 5305W	Pilot whale	Pilot whale swimming close to shore for several days. Locals concerned about its health. Animal not resighted
21 st to 20 th October	Catalina, Bonavista Bay 4829N, 5305W	Harbour porpoise	Stranding, eventually dying
8 th November	Green Island, Port Union, Bonavista Bay. 4830N, 5302W	Large whale spp;	Large dead whale floating. Unable to contact notices to shipping but reported to Jackie Kean and Conservation Officers.
12 th November	Clay Cove, Westport 4943N, 5641W	Sperm whale	Dead on beach. Seen on Google Earth by Facebook group. Picture seems to be from 2022.
20 th November	Comfort Cove, Notre Dame Bay.	Blue shark	Dead on beach
20 th November	Loon Bay, Notre Dame Bay. 4916N, 5450W	Blue shark	Dead on beach
23 rd November	Keels Cove, Bonavista Bay. 4836N, 5324W	White beaked dolphin	Dead, emaciated on beach
30 th November	Back Beach, Lumsden, Newtown, Bonavista Bay. 4932N, 5364W	Humpback	Dead on beach. Reported by hikers

Table 4. Miscellaneous marine animals reported in Newfoundland and Labrador during 2024

Date	Area	Species	Description
8 th July	Chance Cove, Trinity Bay.	Beluga	Adult beluga feeding on caplin

11 th August	Back Cove, Fogo, Fogo Island. 4943N, 5418W	Northern right whale	Feeding in cove. Requested Conservation Officers to photo and sent pictures to New England Aquarium for ID
1 st , 2 nd and 3 rd September	Trinity Bay. 4821N, 5319W	3 Blue whales	3 blue whale reported and photo Identified by Sea of Whales tour boat

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1-888-895-3003

If you have a WHALE or TURTLE or basking shark (live or dead) caught in your fishing gear, call this toll-free number and we will respond with a trained team. If you see any whales, turtles or dolphins (live or dead) on a beach, please call. Should you see any leatherback sea turtles please call.

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Appendix II

